

DEVELOPING A DIGITAL PRESERVATION DEPARTMENT IN AN AUDIOVISUAL ARCHIVE: PERSPECTIVES ON ADAPTIVE AND INTERDISCIPLINARY CHANGE

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This paper explores the development of a dedicated Digital Preservation Department at the National Film and Sound Archive of Australia (NFSA) within the broader context of the institution's ambitious digital transformation. Framed through a Complex Adaptive Systems (CAS) lens, the research examines how interdisciplinary collaboration, reciprocal knowledge exchange, and organisational memory contribute to adaptive change. Through a reflexive, practice-led methodology grounded in the perspectives of staff across operational, strategic, and executive levels, the paper highlights the evolving ecology of digital preservation at the NFSA. It offers a critical, situated account of the challenges, structural shifts, and emerging strategies shaping digital preservation in a national audiovisual archive and advocates for an adaptive, systems-oriented approach to managing complex digital heritage.

Keywords - Strategy, Collaboration, Governance, People, Adaptive Change

Conference Topics - Haerenga - Journey

I. INTRODUCTION

Audiovisual archives worldwide are undergoing a significant transformation as they adapt to the challenges and opportunities presented by digital technologies. This shift is not only technical but social and temporal, requiring archives to rethink preservation strategies, access models, and organisational structures to remain responsive to rapidly evolving media formats, user expectations, and technological infrastructures.

Audiovisual media dominate the ways people connect, learn and share in the 21st century, with

digital platforms accelerating both the creation and consumption of content. This growth has expanded the NFSA's responsibilities as custodian of Australia's audiovisual memory, requiring us to address rapidly changing digital formats, rising storage demands and long-term sustainability expectations. For more than 90 years, the NFSA has preserved and shared Australia's audiovisual history, stewarding a unique national cultural asset. Today, this role extends beyond safeguarding physical and digital collections: it requires actively responding to technological innovation, global standards, and the environmental and cultural contexts in which preservation takes place.

To meet these challenges, the NFSA has embedded digital responsiveness across its leadership and activities, ensuring that technology underpins collecting, preservation, access and organisational capability. At the same time, the NFSA is reshaping how audiences connect with the national collection, through a stronger focus on digital platforms, new modes of storytelling and a commitment to reflecting Australia's diversity and cultural dynamism. These strategies, supported by investment in digital infrastructure, research, and audience development, ensure that our national audiovisual collection is not only preserved but also used for learning, inspiration and entertainment, across the broadest possible range of communities and platforms [1].

In this paper, we share the complex and evolving nature of developing and embedding a Digital Preservation Department at the NFSA in this time of ambitious digital transformation. We have drawn upon Complex Adaptive Systems (CAS) approaches as a useful framework for positioning interdisciplinary collaboration, navigating organisational change and responding to the growing complexity of digital preservation. This paper also serves as an organisational advocacy tool, framing the emerging story of digital preservation at the NFSA and making visible the labour, strategy, and collaboration underpinning its development.

II. BACKGROUND

The NFSA is the country's national audiovisual cultural institution, responsible for collecting, preserving, and sharing Australia's film, sound, and broadcast heritage. Although the collection dates to the mid-1930s, the NFSA in its current form was established in 1984. The NFSA's collections include over a million unique works – including moving image, recorded sound, games, software, immersive digital media, objects, and contextual materials that reflect Australia's audiovisual cultural history. As both a cultural institution and a part of the Australian Government, it plays a vital role in safeguarding audiovisual heritage while responding to the challenges of digital preservation, access, and technological change.

The preservation of digital heritage has long been part of the NFSA's remit, well before the establishment of a dedicated Digital Preservation Department. The emergence of digital collections was not a disruptive break from analogue preservation practices but evolved alongside the NFSA's early adoption of digitisation as a preservation tool. Internal documentation records that between 2006 and 2009, a proposal titled *The Digital Deluge* formally recognised the need for dedicated digital archiving infrastructure and expertise. Although the proposal was not implemented, it laid the conceptual groundwork for subsequent developments. The international call to action has since reinforced this recognition articulated in *Deadline 2025* [2], which underscores the urgency of digitising and digitally preserving magnetic media before it becomes irretrievably inaccessible due to format obsolescence and material degradation.

By 2011, the NFSA had introduced a Quantum Scalar Tape Library and a media asset management system (MediaFlex) to securely store and manage digital and physical content. Early digital preservation activity – focused on quality control and format management – was led by the Information Communication Technology (ICT) department and driven by in-house digitisation and growing volumes of born-digital material. These efforts reflected the NFSA's evolving and responsive engagement with global shifts in audiovisual heritage. Today, the NFSA adds over two petabytes of material annually, making the need for a well-resourced, strategically positioned Digital Preservation Department more urgent than ever.

III. THEORETICAL APPARATUS

Within the digital preservation community, it is well established that such cross-boundary collaboration is essential to building resilience and sustainability. Established and evolving audit and assessment frameworks – including ISO 16363: Audit and Certification of Trustworthy Digital Repositories (TDR) [3], the OAIS Reference Model (ISO 14721) [4], the Digital Preservation Capability Maturity Model (DPCMM) [5], the NDSA Levels of Digital Preservation [6], and more recent tools including the DPC Rapid Assessment Model (RAM) [7] and the DPC Competency Framework [8] with its accompanying Competency Audit Toolkit (CAT v2) [9] – demonstrate that digital preservation spans technical, organisational, and policy domains. They make evident the diverse forms preservation activities take, and the well-recognised interdisciplinary nature of the field, where success depends on collaboration across teams.

Building on this shared foundation, our work introduces a Complex Adaptive Systems (CAS) lens to further examine how interdisciplinary collaboration, organisational change, and the growing complexity of digital preservation can be better understood and navigated. Rather than serving as a guiding model for development, CAS is applied here retrospectively as an interpretive perspective. This distinction matters: we are not claiming that the NFSA has consciously adopted CAS as its primary roadmap; rather, its concepts provide a valuable lens for reflecting on past and current practices while intentionally shaping digital preservation through collaboration.

Re-contextualising the broad tradition of CAS scholarship allows for the conceptualisation of digital collections as dynamic systems composed of diverse agents – departments, teams, individuals, workflows, policies, stakeholders – whose interactions generate adaptive change over time. At the macro level, these systems respond to external pressures through exchanges of knowledge, resources, and evolving standards. At the micro level, individual agents adapt practices and tools through iterative, non-linear interactions [10] [11]. CAS provides a valuable theoretical apparatus for critically engaging in the early stages of establishing a dedicated Digital Preservation Department – an active, evolving process that involves bringing together two pre-existing teams. Rather than implementing a static blueprint, this approach views organisational change as emergent, co-constructed, and dependent on fostering reciprocal knowledge exchange across disciplines [12]. Its approach positions digital preservation not only as a technical or procedural challenge, but as a collaborative and adaptive archival practice; one that is embedded in and shaped by the wider institutional ecology. Human-centred approaches strengthen this view by emphasising the role of staff, stakeholders, and users in shaping preservation priorities and ensuring that systems and services are responsive to the communities they serve.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This research adopts a qualitative, reflexive methodology, grounded in empirical, experiential, and anecdotal evidence from within the Digital Branch of the NFSA. It draws on the perspectives of three staff – Hannah Lamond (Collections Digital Services Officer), Jaye Weatherburn (Head of Digital Preservation), and Keir Winesmith (Chief Digital Officer) – representing operational, departmental, and executive levels. These varied viewpoints echo the multi-layered nature of institutional change and, in line with a CAS framework, reflect upon how collective behaviour emerges from the interactions of diverse agents within a system. By writing this paper collaboratively, we are not just analysing CAS – we are enacting it. The research is further informed by institutional memory, drawn from informal conversations, interviews with long-serving staff, and internal documentation, all of which provide critical context for understanding how digital preservation practice has evolved. Attending to this embodied

knowledge highlights that digital transformation is built on more than infrastructure; it is built upon human-centred approaches that demand strong intentionality.

V. HISTORICAL JOURNEY

The introduction of a media asset management system in 2011 and the infrastructure to support the storage of a growing digital collection created increased complexities in the broader institutional departments responsible for the stewardship of the collection. In 2013, internal documentation outlining 'New Directions in Digital Acquisitions and Accessioning', identified the current issues in the archiving processes of digital media and proposed solutions. The document posited that the new media asset management system and surge in digital acquisitions exposed gaps in digital knowledge and infrastructure, disrupting consistent workflows and compromising digital preservation efforts. Central to the vast challenges identified was a renewed call for digital expertise. This specialised knowledge was to serve a dual purpose: to undertake the processing of incoming digital materials (quarantine, validation, and integrity-checking) and provide technical training to staff responsible for digital media acquisitions. Together, these efforts aimed to directly address existing knowledge gaps.

Between 2017 and 2019, responding to calls for digital expertise and an unsustainable portfolio of responsibilities, a Digital Collection Technical Support role was implemented within a team of three, the Digital Collection Infrastructure (DCI) team. The creation of this position answered some of the concerns that were highlighted in 2013. The DCI team, however, had an extensive portfolio of responsibilities that was unsustainable long-term, requiring specialised expertise across the teams' remit of responsibilities covering digital collection workflows, digital infrastructure, and digital preservation development. In response to this, there was an executive decision to form a separate team, Collection Digital Services (CDS), to continue to advance digital processes and digital preservation development. The digital infrastructure responsibilities of the previous DCI team were then moved into the ICT department.

In 2023, the NFSA created a single Digital branch, which included activities that are often in separate branches within an audiovisual archive. The new

branch included ICT, digital platform development, data analysis, enterprise program management, collection system management, digital collection services and research. At the same time, a new Chief Digital Officer role was created and added to the senior executive team. For the first time, digital was positioned centrally within the institution.

VI. THE ECOLOGY OF DIGITAL ARCHIVING AT THE NFSA

A. *The Digital Preservation Department*

In early 2024, the NFSA increased its investment in digital preservation, adding new junior and senior positions. By August, two existing teams were consolidated into a dedicated Digital Preservation section within the Digital Branch. Building upon NFSA's existing strategic commitment to digital preservation, this structural change demonstrated clear intent and aim to set the organisation up for generational success in preserving and providing access for Australia's audiovisual heritage – a heritage that is increasing in its digital complexity. The establishment of the Digital Preservation section included the appointment of a new department head, with the structure of this department currently retaining the division of two existing teams: Collection Digital Services and Collection Systems. This structural transformation also built on the NFSA's existing strategic commitment to digital preservation through recruitment and staff capacity building, and software and hardware procurement and integration.

The role of the Collection Digital Services (CDS) team is to develop and undertake digital processes in collaboration with curatorial and ICT teams including: the secure data extraction of

obsolete and contemporary digital carriers; the compliance and integrity of digital objects; the selection and recommendation of digital object formats and standards; and quality assurance and control. CDS also engages and advises internal and external stakeholder specialists within the audiovisual and electronic entertainment industry and archives.

The Collection Systems (CS) team is responsible for the management of systems and platforms for the NFSA physical and digital collection, in collaboration with curatorial and ICT teams. Historically, the team's work has focused on the media asset management system MediaFlex; however, it has recently diversified to reflect the incorporation of additional systems. The team is increasingly involved in automated management of file and metadata management via custom orchestration. The breadth of these requirements is reflected in a broad skill set exhibited by the team, which stretches from typical ICT tasks to highly complex and specialised metadata analysis. This work includes awareness of international standards practices, as well as the ability to arrive at customised coding solutions where traditional tooling is not sufficient.

B. *Situating Digital Archival Practice*

At the NFSA, the management of digital heritage unfolds within a complex network of specialised teams. In audiovisual archiving practice at the NFSA, digitisation is considered a method of preservation, with this preservation ensuring long-term accessibility and maximum integrity, and particularly in the digital context, it is increasingly recognised as a continuous, evolving process – 'a never-ending management task' [13]. It relies on

Fig. 1 Distributed network of the teams involved in the preservation of digital media at the NFSA

sustained human effort, resources, and infrastructure, exemplified by the axiom that *nothing is preserved, only being preserved* [14].

Preservation, when viewed holistically in this way, extends well beyond the boundaries of a digital preservation department. *Fig. 1* visualises a distributed network diagram of the multi-disciplinary nature of digital archiving practice at the NFSA, where responsibilities are embedded across a web of interconnected teams. Digitisation services (as a methodology of preservation with digital outputs), curatorial and accessioning units, ICT infrastructure, digital platforms, data analysis, and access pathways are all entangled in dynamic relationships that sustain the digital collection. Interactions across these functions reveal a system of shared responsibilities, where preservation outcomes emerge from ongoing collaboration, coordinated workflows and the constant negotiation of priorities and expertise.

As digital becomes increasingly central to the NFSA's remit, this ecosystem continues to expand. Where analogue once dominated, the collection pathway has now forked; digital sits alongside analogue but increasingly defines the direction of preservation practice. This shift has forged stronger relationships between Digital Preservation and other teams whose work is tied to digital outcomes.

This evolving landscape is also reflected in the current distribution of staff. *Fig. 2* presents a quantitative view of the personnel engaged across NFSA's digital ecosystem, illustrating both the breadth of roles contributing to preservation outcomes and therefore the importance of dedicated digital preservation expertise. While each team brings distinct perspectives and responsibilities, Digital Preservation plays a stewardship role: embodying the "preserve" principle of the NFSA's mission – *Collect, Preserve, Share, Promote* – in the digital domain. This position requires not only technical capability but also the ability to work across multiple audiences in the institution, shaping workflows and priorities through collaboration.

This ecosystem underscores the need for explicit digital archiving and digital preservation policies, procedures, and expertise to be coordinated and integrated into the broader preservation landscape at the NFSA, and supported

Fig. 2. Distribution of staff across NFSA's digital ecosystem, highlighting the breadth of roles contributing to preservation and the stewardship role of Digital Preservation

by clear governance, roles and responsibilities, continuous improvement structures, and ongoing skills and education development. To support the ambitious digital transformation underway, digital archiving and preservation workflows require interdisciplinary input and collaborative approaches to develop new ways of working together.

VII. EMERGING JOURNEY

In 2024-2025, an ambitious digital transformation agenda for the NFSA has seen the increasing need for changing approaches and ways of working required for accessioning, acquisition, ingest, and ongoing digital collection care management for digitised and complex born-digital materials. In addition, a shift to a 'proactive' collecting approach to support the scale and diversity of social video, and the complex processes and skills required for the work, has also forged the need for new internal connections across business units, and effective coordination of effort and understanding.

The skills required for digital forensics work (extracting digital content from obsolete media) often involve a curious and open mindset, problem-solving ability, and communication in seeking useful information from external networks and communities. There is also a need for continual advocacy in communicating to internal teams and leadership to showcase the time and effort required for this work.

A recent example that highlights both the curious complexity of digital preservation and the need for clarity around delivered outcomes was work conducted on an acquisition of 3.5-inch floppy discs containing personal, private and sensitive material.

Preservation of this legacy media was undertaken through migration via imaging techniques, arduous and time-consuming digital forensics, and emulation. Working closely with curatorial and accessioning staff, the process quickly demonstrated a misalignment in the governing philosophies of the digital preservation and curatorial selection policies. Where enacting the retention of maximum integrity requires bit-for-bit preservation of the original carrier, ethical selection practices call for this integrity to be compromised through the modification of the floppy disc images to deselect personal material. As the creation of disk images for this content also aids capture and preservation for essential metadata that could otherwise be lost, a key need is highlighted through this example: born-digital archiving workflows to maximise understanding and future access to the content necessitate considering changes to existing archival practices. Using CAS as a reflective model, this example demonstrates how adaptive change can emerge from interdisciplinary tensions, and how collaborative problem-solving across micro-level agents can catalyse new organisational practices and policy shifts. Such tensions mark not an impasse but a beginning, pointing the way toward more collaborative and adaptive models of digital archival practice.

VIII. CURRENT STATE

A. *Constraints and Realities*

The strategic merging of two existing teams to form the Digital Preservation Department has provided a strong foundation and valuable institutional knowledge from the outset. However, it also introduces constraints that affect the pace of progress. Both teams carry significant business-as-usual responsibilities, making long-term activities – like research, identity formation, and strategic planning – additional to their core workload. This is further compounded by the fact that fifty percent of the team is new within the past year. While this has brought diverse knowledge and added capacity, integration, knowledge building, and learning new workflows take time. Additionally, embedding digital preservation across the organisation requires ongoing trust-building and alignment with established structures, which depend upon sustained dialogue and engagement. These realities continue to shape both the potential and limitations of our current trajectory.

B. *Adaptive Change and Interdisciplinary Approaches*

Our efforts are focused on actively building the presence and identity of the Digital Preservation Department both within the institutional framework of the NFSA and the broader preservation community. A key goal is to demystify the digital preservation process, at both operational and strategic, and executive levels.

1. *Operational Perspective*

On an operational level, contributions to developing a dedicated digital preservation department centre around an overarching ethos that awareness and inclusiveness create valuable synergies. Our practical application of this principle manifests in three key strategies: reciprocal knowledge exchange, horizontal inter-departmental working groups, and systematic documentation.

Reciprocal Knowledge Exchange in Practice

Reciprocal knowledge exchange is a cornerstone of our approach, designed to break down silos and create trust across departments. Rather than relying on a selective, trickle-down model where information is filtered through a few representatives, we have experimented with open forums where all staff from invited departments are welcome. These sessions create space for questions, clarification, and dialogue, enabling knowledge to circulate more directly and transparently. They encourage curiosity and strengthen relationships between colleagues who might not otherwise work together, fostering the trust and reassurance needed to approach the complex challenges of working with digital material.

A tangible example is our collaboration with the Accessioning team. We have been gradually detailing their most frequently asked questions – notably, format types, association structures, and checksums – culminating in a more formal dialogue to share our expertise. In parallel, we seek to better understand accessioning workflows and media asset management configurations. This two-way consultation ensures that our contributions align with their needs and that their insights inform our practices.

This approach reflects horizontal, cross-disciplinary collaboration practised through functional-teamwork models at international institutions such as the San Francisco Museum of Modern Art [15]. It also enacts key principles of the

CAS framework. Through co-evolution [16], teams adapt in response to one another, creating feedback loops that drive change; through emergence [17], these interactions give rise to new practices and shared understandings that could not have been predicted in isolation. They recognise that institutional resilience is built not only on technical expertise, but on people's capacity to navigate uncertainty, share knowledge, and adapt collaboratively. Teams with aligned goals, who work transparently and generously, can remake antiquated or broken systems from the inside out, without the need for executive or expert external intervention.

Horizontal Working Groups

Alongside open knowledge exchange, we are engaged in targeted horizontal collaboration through inter-departmental working groups. One such group is focused on standardising how digital heritage is archived as it passes through curatorial, accessioning, and preservation teams. Its purpose is to establish robust channels of communication so that critical information flows cyclically: from Digital Preservation to Curatorial, from Curatorial to Accessioning, and back again, with access considerations present at every stage.

This collaboration gives digital preservation a stronger platform for input into the stewardship of the collection. Technical expertise around quality and integrity now feeds directly into how curatorial decisions are made and how digital heritage is structured and accessed in the media asset management system. In turn, curatorial and accessioning perspectives shape preservation processes, ensuring solutions evolve in dialogue rather than being imposed as disruptive shifts. This balance reflects an adaptive approach: digital preservation expertise enhances and refines existing practices, while remaining attentive to the realities of implementation across teams.

The working group also reflects lessons from the NFSA's historical journey. Earlier documentation highlighted communication gaps between departments, and various initiatives have since sought to address these challenges in different ways. This group is a current expression of that ongoing effort – not the first, nor the last – demonstrating how working with digital heritage is necessarily iterative, complex, and evolving.

Our position in this working group embeds digital preservation intentionally across the continuum of collection care [18]. This ensures that technical integrity is considered alongside curatorial selection, that workflows are mutually informed, and that preservation knowledge is integrated rather than siloed. By bringing together representatives from across departments, the working group makes explicit that stewardship of digital heritage is a shared responsibility; iterative, adaptive, and grounded in diverse expertise.

Documentation as Biography

The third pillar of our operational approach is systematic documentation. Documenting digital preservation processes and workflows serves as an integral foundation for sustainable and reflective practice. This work upholds the continued development of consistent workflows and outcomes across the team, while acknowledging that preservation requirements are not static and differ depending on format-specific or project-based demands. Beyond internal consistency, documentation also functions as a tool for transparency and collaboration. It enables us to demystify digital preservation for other departments within the organisation and tangibly share knowledge with external institutions facing similar challenges.

Critically, our documentation efforts are both forward-looking and historically aware. This practice supports generational success by capturing the sociotechnical and temporal context in which our methodologies have emerged – recognising that standards, infrastructure and resources will inevitably evolve. As in museological practice, where documentation serves a methodology of traceable care [19], our records form a 'biography' of digital preservation at the NFSA. They enable us, and those who follow, to identify how our preservation practices shift over time in response to decisions, standards, and infrastructure that define our work today.

2. Strategic Perspective

Comprehensive policies and strategic direction at an institutional level provide the foundation for developing a digital preservation capability at the NFSA.

At the broadest level, the Australian Government's National Cultural Policy, "Revive", is a five-year plan to revive the arts in Australia. At the

heart of this policy is the goal to ensure there is a place for every story, and a story for every place [20]. Each of the pillars detailed in this policy inform digital transformation and digital preservation capability building at the NFSA, "First Nations First", "A Place for Every Story", "Centrality of the Artist", "Strong Cultural Infrastructure" and "Engaging the Audience".

The Strategic Direction 2022–25 [21] outlines the NFSA's specific priorities to 2025, with a revision and update for this strategy currently underway. This strategy features three key priorities that guide digital work: Relevance (A national audiovisual collection that tells Australia's stories in all their diversity, evolving with industry and audiences and adapting to reflect new technologies and content); Reach (A widely-used collection readily discoverable by all Australians); and Revenue (A forward-thinking and original institutional brand trusted and loved by its growing audience).

The Digital Master Plan 2027 (internal document under development at the time of writing) reasserts the NFSA's strategic focus on digital transformation by setting out a digital capability growth roadmap through to 2027. The Master Plan also details ongoing sustainment of new digital infrastructure and practices currently being developed by the NFSA.

In response to this policy and strategy landscape that the NFSA exists within, developing a dedicated Digital Preservation Department in an audiovisual archive at a strategic level benefits from an interdisciplinary approach. This includes looking to fields such as change management and communications for developing effective strategies for organisational change and adaptation, to support the emerging needs of managing complex digital materials for preservation and access with a long-term lens.

Communication is key internally and externally for advancing digital preservation capability. For internal communications, a digital preservation presence on the NFSA intranet is essential, and we have developed a strategy for publishing regular 'news' posts with an education and awareness framing for work underway. These communications not only inform but activate feedback loops, encouraging an agile flow of information across teams and enabling responsive

adjustment in practice [22]. Externally we have found that by establishing regular local informal in-person meetings with other organisations in the local region, our ability to talk through common challenges creates a culture of sharing knowledge and expertise that can be utilised effectively to solve pressing issues. Developing and leveraging networks for change in this way can aid fundamental organisational change, as this change often involves learning and adapting at local levels. Building network connections within and outside the organisation can facilitate knowledge sharing, sense-making, and the appropriation of changes. Encouraging dialogue and connectivity is a key role for management during change, as "human behaviour and understanding are guided by contextually determined interpretive schemes, norms, and power relationships that shape sense making" [23] [24] [25].

Work has begun developing a dedicated digital preservation strategy for the NFSA, one that aligns with broader organisational strategy and planning. The goal is to publish this strategy in 2025 to share our approach and thinking with the digital preservation community nationally and internationally. The NFSA has many roles: it is a part of the Australian public service, it is a cultural audiovisual archive, it is a venue in Canberra, and it is a media producer, distributor and licensee. These multifaceted organisational identities are supported by staff in different departments, with different understandings and applications of terminology such as "digital", "preservation", and "access". Developing a digital preservation strategy alongside new ways of working, new approaches, and broad digital transformation necessitates a "conversational organisation". A conversational organisation being one that has effective cross-cutting communication mechanisms and coordination that can effectively bridge across domains to build trust, exchange needs, and develop a shared language as a foundation for generational change activities.

The concept of institutional memory (or organisational memory) can also inform how change is approached by understanding past experiences, successes, and failures. Retaining institutional memories through detailed records and documentation is essential (e.g. internal documentation and anecdotal evidence from the experience of long-serving staff). Institutional

memory can therefore provide the context within which new changes are introduced. It includes the organisation's history, values, traditions, and established routines. Embedded within the CAS framework is the notion that change initiatives that align with existing context and build upon it may be more readily accepted. Conversely, changes that disregard the organisation's history or culture might face greater resistance [26]. Building this concept into change strategies for digital transformation and digital preservation capability building is one way to aid advancing strategies for digital archiving and preservation.

IX. CONCLUSION

The development of a dedicated Digital Preservation Department at the NFSA reflects not only a structural shift but a strategic, system-wide effort to embed adaptive, collaborative, and sustainable digital preservation practices. By using CAS as a lens to foster intentionality in this work, our research to date highlights how meaningful change emerges through reciprocity, iteration, and a deep understanding of the institutional context.

Looking ahead, our focus remains on continued reciprocal exchange, both within the NFSA and with external partners, as we navigate the evolving complexities of digital preservation. Maintaining open dialogue and fostering solution-oriented approaches will be central to how we balance the preservation of emerging content formats – such as social media, games, and other complex digital media – and curatorial collection strategies. This commitment also includes deepening partnerships beyond the institution to inform and strengthen our approaches to preserving born-digital and interactive media. Key priorities in 2025 are the co-development and publication of the Digital Master Plan 2027 and the NFSA's Digital Preservation Strategy, which will articulate the shared principles and strategic direction needed to support the NFSA's ambitious digital transformation goals regarding preservation and access over time. In parallel, we are actively collaborating with curatorial colleagues to address the challenges of collecting and preserving social video, and to develop shared frameworks for software and games preservation.

When considering the field and the practice of digital preservation through the lens of CAS, it is also valuable to acknowledge how other cross-

disciplinary organisational research frameworks could also deepen our understanding of the challenges faced by cultural institutions. Valuable future research directions could incorporate learnings from frameworks such as socio-technical systems (STS) theory (historically articulated by Trist and Bamforth (1951) [27] and later reflected upon by Mumford (2006) [28] and Walker (2015) [29] for considering technological infrastructures and human actors as inseparable, co-evolving elements of organisational practice. The concept of boundary objects / boundary-spanning theory [30] could be utilised to illustrate how “boundary objects” such as shared standards, models, and tools enable collaboration across disciplinary and institutional divides (e.g. the role of standards such as OAIS or PREMIS, which act as shared points of reference enabling archivists, ICT staff, and curators to work together despite differing professional languages and priorities). Additionally, and perhaps most critically, resilience and socio-ecological models [31] could potentially illuminate how institutions navigate cycles of technological change, obsolescence, and renewal, and how adaptive strategies can ensure continuity through disruption. By looking to these frameworks alongside CAS, we open the door to discussion on their more explicit integration in future research as the field matures.

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